

Table 2. Salicylic, chlorogenic, and gallic acids in healthy (H) and thrips-infested (I) plants of resistant and susceptible rice varieties.

Variety	mg/g fresh weight of leaves					
	Salicylic ^a		Chlorogenic ^b		Gallic ^b	
	H	I	H	I	H	I
<i>Resistant</i>						
Ptb 21	0.22	0.30	2.40	2.32	0.84	1.16
Mozhikaruppu	0.20	0.33	2.48	2.80	1.20	0.96
Kandagasalai	0.31	0.29	1.92	2.80	1.20	0.60
CO 3	0.30	0.25	2.48	2.48	1.00	1.00
TNRI	0.27	0.28	2.56	1.84	0.96	0.64
IR62	0.31	0.30	2.32	1.84	0.80	0.60
Mean	0.27	0.29	2.36	2.35	1.00	0.83
<i>Susceptible</i>						
Bhavani	0.64	0.60	1.44	1.30	0.40	0.36
IR8	0.76	0.77	1.36	1.34	0.40	0.41
IR26	0.60	0.59	1.44	1.40	0.40	0.38
IR34	0.56	0.57	0.94	1.10	0.38	0.32
ADT38	0.61	0.63	1.48	1.00	0.60	0.50
CO 43	0.55	0.57	1.52	1.60	0.38	0.42
Vani	0.68	0.69	1.04	1.24	0.24	0.30
Mean	0.63	0.63	1.32	1.28	0.40	0.38

^aSalicylic acid separated and estimated through silica-gel TLC using chloroform: acetic acid (9:1 vol/vol) solvent system.

^bChlorogenic and gallic acids separated on silica-gel using methanol: acetic acid: water (9:1:1 vol/vol) solvent system.

Resistance to rice gall midge (GM) in Kerala, India

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We evaluated 135 varieties against GM *Orseolia oryzae*. Damage was very severe during 1988 wet season (Jun-Jul to Oct-Nov) in the nursery and in the

field and during 1989 dry season (Dec-Jan to Apr-May) in the field.

Test varieties were grown in 10-m² plots with two replications. Recommended agronomic practices were followed. Silvershoots in 10 randomly selected hills from each replication were counted at 30 d after transplanting.

IET10745 (C1924/RP9-4) showed high resistance, 10 lines showed moderate resistance (see table).

Resistance to rice GM in Kerala, India, 1988-89.

Line	Parentage	Score ^a		
		1988 wet season	1989 dry season	Mean
IET11070	Pusa 2-21/WGL 28171	3	2	2.5
IET11581	Rajendra/IR30	3	3	3.0
IET10745	C1924/RP9-4	0	0	0
IET10750	Asha/Kranthi	3	2	2.5
IET10726	Phalgune/Ptb 21	3	1	2.0
IET10314	IR62/Parmel	3	3	3.0
IET10847	PR106/OBS528	3	1	2.0
IET11451	Vikram/Mashin	3	2	2.5
IET11160	Ratna/ARC10659	3	3	3.0
IET11464	Ratna/ARC5984	3	2	2.5
IET11465	Ratna/ARC5984	3	1	2.5
	TN1 (susceptible check)	9	9	9

^a Standard evaluation system for rice 0-9 scale: 0 = no damage, 9 = more than 25% infected tillers.

Resistance of rice to green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* in free-choice and no-choice tests

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To identify resistance to planthoppers and leafhoppers, rice germplasm is commonly screened under a free-choice bulk seedling test that easily separates highly resistant and susceptible germplasm. However, the test is not completely reliable in differentiating genetic resistance from "pseudoresistance" resulting from escape or uneven distribution of insects in the seedling trays.

We compared free-choice and no-choice tests using the reactions of 28 rice varieties with known or unknown genes for GLH resistance. TN1 was the susceptible check.

Seeds were sown in 70- × 50- × 10-cm wooden trays in 12-cm-long rows with 6 cm spacing between rows. Each tray had three strips of rows. Seedlings were thinned at 7 d to 15/row and infested with 3d-instar nymphs. Each tray represented a replication.

The free-choice test involved two approaches. In one, seedlings in each tray were infested by tapping GLH nymph-infested TN1 plants so that each seedling tray received about 5 nymphs/seedling. Infested seedlings were kept uncovered. In the second approach, each seedling tray was covered with a 70- × 50- × 70-cm nylon mesh cage. A precise number of 3d instars (5 nymphs/seedling) were introduced using a glass-blowing tube.

In test one, nymphs could move to different varieties in the tray and could move out of the tray. In test two, nymphs were forced to choose among the varieties within the enclosed tray.

Nymphs were counted at 1 and 3 d after infestation (DAI) and damage was recorded at 10 d on a row basis. TN1 was completely killed after DAI.

In the no-choice test, 10 pregerminated seeds/row were sown for each variety. At 7 d, each row was covered with a 13- × 4- × 27-cm rectangular

mylar cage with nylon mesh windows on the sides and top. Rows were infested with 5 3d-instar nymphs/seedling. Damage was recorded at 10 DAI.

In both the open and covered free-choice tests, nymphs settled in uneven numbers (see table). Significantly more nymphs were counted on susceptible varieties. Jingasail, Ptb 8, and IR42 showed moderate resistance.

In the covered test, however, Jhingasail, Ptb 8, and IR42 that had numbers of nymphs comparable with that on susceptible TN1 and showed susceptible reactions. More nymphs were recorded on varieties in the covered test and damage ratings differed significantly for varieties Jhingasail, Godalki, IR8, Ptb 8, ARC7012, TAPL 796, IR36, and Moddai Karuppan.

Damage in the open tests was lower because fewer nymphs settled on those varieties. Damage increased when the varieties were infested with nymphs at a density that killed TN1. Damage ratings between covered free-choice and no-choice tests were comparable, except for IR22 which was susceptible in covered test and highly susceptible in no-choice test.

Our results show that the no-choice test is useful for identifying true resistance. However, the method is laborious and unsuitable for mass evaluation. One procedure would be to screen for most of the susceptible germplasm using the open free-choice

GLH nymphs settling on seedlings of susceptible and resistant rice varieties grown in a free-choice test with open and covered seedboxes, and damage ratings in free-choice tests and no-choice tests where seedling rows were separated by mylar film cages.^a IRR1, 1988.

Variety	Resistance gene	Nymphs settled (no./15 seedlings)*				Damage ratings at 10 DAI**		
		Free choice				Free choice		No choice
		Open		Covered		Open	Covered	
		1 DAI	3 DAI	1 DAI	3DAI			
Pankhari 203	3 <i>Glh</i> 1	10 f-h	6 hi	28 fg	13 k-m	1.7 a	2.3 a	1.7 a
Jhingasail	<i>Glh</i> 1	20 c-e	24 b	87 ac	66 ad	5.0 b	8.3 a	8.3 a
ASD 7	<i>Glh</i> 2	17 c-f	12 d-g	13 j-l	15 j-l	3.0 a	3.0 a	3.0 a
Palasithari 601	<i>Glh</i> 2	10 gh	13 c-f	33 f	21 ij	3.0 a	3.0 a	3.0 a
Godalki	<i>Glh</i> 2	20 c-e	28 b	55 de	46 c-f	6.3 b	9.0 a	9.0 a
H5	<i>Glh</i> 3	24c	19 b-d	89 ab	68 a-c	6.3 a	8.3 a	8.3 a
IR8	<i>Glh</i> 3	22 cd	26 b	56 de	47 c-f	5.7 b	9.0 a	9.0 a
DNJ 97	<i>Glh</i> 3	42 b	45 a	77 b-d	79 ab	7.7 a	9.0 a	8.3 a
Ptb 8	<i>glh</i> 4	25 c	25 b	76 b-d	72 ab	5.0 b	7.7 a	7.7 a
IR42	<i>glh</i> 4	20 c-e	28 b	49 e	68 a-c	5.7 a	7.7 a	7.7 a
ARC7012	<i>glh</i> 4	24 c	18 b-e	61 b-e	51 b-e	5.0 b	8.3 a	8.3 a
ASD8	<i>Glh</i> 5	17 c-g	18 b-e	91	13 k-m	3.0 a	3.0 a	3.0 a
Bhawalia	<i>Glh</i> 5	19 c-e	13 c-f	26 fg	22 hi	5.0 a	5.0 a	5.7 a
TAPL 796	<i>Glh</i> 6	21 c-e	12 e-g	32 fg	33 f-h	4.3 b	5.7 a	6.3 a
IR36	<i>Glh</i> 6	23 cd	15 c-f	56 de	44 d-f	3.0 b	6.3 a	6.3 a
Ptb 18	<i>Glh</i> 1+6	6i	5i	14 j-l	6 p	1.7 a	2.3 a	3.0 a
Moddai Karuppan	<i>Glh</i> 7	14 d-h	20 bc	59 c-e	38 e-g	4.3 b	5.7 a	5.0 a
Bazal	<i>Glh</i> 2+5	16 c-g	12 e-g	51 de	36 e-g	5.0 a	4.3 a	5.0 a
Lasane	<i>Glh</i> 2+5	14 d-h	11 fg	29 fg	27 g-i	3.0 a	3.7 a	3.0 a
Laki 659	<i>Glh</i> 3+5	9 h	11 fg	11 kl	8 n-p	3.0 a	3.0 a	2.3 a
IR22	No gene	56 ab	51 a	67 b-e	64 b-d	8.3 ab	7.0 b	9.0 a
IR62	?	16 c-g	15 c-f	16 i-k	14 kl	3.7 a	3.0 a	3.0 a
IR64	?	17 c-f	10 fg	14 jk	13 k-m	3.0 a	3.0 a	3.0 a
IR66	?	13 e-h	11 fg	11 kl	9 m-o	3.0 a	3.0 a	3.0 a
IR68	?	15 c-g	13 c-f	17 h-j	11 l-n	3.0 a	3.0 a	3.0 a
IR70	?	14 d-h	13 c-f	23 f-h	19 i-k	3.0 a	3.0 a	3.0 a
IR72	?	8 h	8 gh	101	7 op	3.0 a	3.0 a	3.0 a
IR74	?	20 c-e	18 b-e	21 g-i	18 i-k	3.0 a	3.7 a	3.0 a
TN1	No gene	71 a	60 a	126 a	101 a	9.0 a	9.0 a	9.0 a

^aValues having a common letter in a column (*) or row (**) are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

test, then verify the resistance of selected entries in the no-choice test. The no-choice test also is useful in studies of inheritance, where the ratios

of resistant to susceptible plants or lines are critical for analyzing the mode of inheritance. □

Multiple resistance of rice varieties to major insect pests at Pondicherry, India

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Resistant rice varieties form the core of integrated management of insect pests. We screened 87 promising advanced breeding lines against insect pests during the 1986 wet season and 71 lines in 1987. Lines were planted in two rows of 20 hills each with one skip row

Multiple resistance of rice varieties to BPH and LF. Pondicherry, India, 1986 and 1987 wet seasons.

Variety	1986		1987		Pests (no.) to which variety was resistant (a)	Seasons (no.) during which variety showed resistance (b)	Multiple resistance index (a x b)
	BPH (no./hill)	LF (%)	BPH (no./hill)	LF (%)			
KD14-1-39	8	9.5	9	4.6	2	2	4
RP2068-18-3-5	7	14.1	2	2.5	2	2	4
CR333-5-2-3	—	—	10	7.2	2	1	2
MO 5	—	—	5	10.6	2	1	2
RP1579-58	9	14.8	6	9.5	2	2	4
RP1579-1633	9	10.4	7	10.0	2	2	4
RP2199-34-37-55-3	—	—	10	10.2	2	1	2
TNAULFR831311	4	0.5	3	7.5	2	2	4
TN1 (check)	71	15.5	40	18.5	0	2	0
IR50 (check)	48	6.2	58	9.1	1	2	2
PY3	6	16.0	3	18.4	1	2	2